

ISic0369

I.Sicily inscription 0369

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 935

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Text after Korhonen 2004 and comparison with photograph

Translation

Side A: Sacred to the spirits of the underworld. Publicia Ifis, lived 68 years.
Publius Pedius Severus, patron built this

Side B: Sacred to the spirits of the underworld. Publius Pedius
Marianus, lived 25 years, and Publicia Ifis. Titus Pedius Severus, the son, lived
18 years. Pedius Severus, Arria Volumnilla the mother, and Caius Pedius
Severus the son, built this.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491580

EDR 140105

EDCS 21900409

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7087 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 122

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